

Synthesis of some *N*-substituted carbazoles and their larvicidal studies

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Manuscript received 28 October 2003, revised 27 July 2004, accepted 2 September 2004

Some *N*-substituted carbazoles have been synthesized and a comparative larvicidal study has also been done on the larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus*.

In continuation of our earlier work¹, in this communication we have reported synthesis of a few more *N*-substituted carbazoles and their larvicidal studies. Schematic formation of the compounds and their structures are given in Scheme 1.

Results and discussion

Larvicidal activity :

Compounds (1-6) were tested for their larvicidal activities at 100 ppm concentration in their pure form at 32 ± 2°C

after 24 h on the 3rd instar larvae of *Culex quinquefasciatus* in water medium. 0.5% of the alcoholic solution of each compound was added in thin stream with gentle stirring into the beaker containing 25 third instar mosquito larvae in water, so that the final concentration of the compound became 100 ppm at 32 ± 2°C. In the similar fashion, same amount of alcohol was added to the control. Few drops of emulsifier were also added to maintain the uniformity of the concentration of the compound in the solution and similar addition was also done in control. Five replications were performed for each set. Percent mortality was calculated after 24 h. No mortality was observed in control. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) calculations were performed for compounds (4-6), which were apparently found not to be equivalent. The order of toxicity was determined by Critical Difference (CD) values, which are 16.83 and 12.00 at 1% and 5% level respectively. From the CD values, the order of toxicity of these compounds can be determined. On the basis of CD and LC₅₀ values, a suitable larvicide may be selected depending upon the availability and economy.

Present toxicity studies show that among all the compounds, *N*-hydroxymethylcarbazole (1) has 100% mortality of mosquito larvae under the conditions mentioned earlier. The LC₅₀ value of (1) is 20.84 ppm which was determined by Probit Analysis.

Though *N*-hydroxymethylcarbazole (1) has highest toxicity among these compounds, whenever the OH group of this compound was replaced by other substituents like acetyl, bromo and *O*-methyl groups, its toxicity rapidly decreased (4) or became nil (2-3). This may be due to the hydrogen bonding effect of hydroxyl group of compound (1)

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Note

with any negative part of the larvae. When the OH group of compound (1) was replaced by other the substituents activity falls, because in these cases no hydrogen bonding takes place.

Though 1,2,3,4,4a,9a-hexahydrocarbazole (*cis*) has no activity, but here some activity was observed in the case of corresponding *N*-acetylated product (6), because it is a carboxamide type compound².

Experimental

The samples were dried over P₂O₅/KOH at 80°C under reduced pressure for 24 h. Melting points of all the samples were taken in sulphuric acid bath in open capillaries and were uncorrected. Reagents used were of Sigma, Aldrich, Fluka, E. Merck, B.D.H., S.D. or S.R.L. Homogeneity of all the samples was tested by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel G coated plate of size 7.5 × 2.5 cm² with different solvents as developer. The positions of the spots on the tlc plates were detected by UV light and in iodine chamber. IR (KBr) and UV (EtOH) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR was recorded in CDCl₃ on Bruker 300 MHz instrument using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. ¹³C NMR was recorded in CDCl₃ and 75 MHz on Bruker 300 MHz instrument using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. All the values in ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra are in δ-scale. Electron impact mass spectra were recorded on Finnigan MAT 8230 mass spectrometer.

N-Hydroxymethylenecarbazole (1) : 0.009 mol of carbazole was dissolved in 20 ml of hot ethanol. To this warm solution, 30 ml of formalin solution was added where by a white precipitate was obtained. To this reaction mixture, 10 ml of 10% sodium hydroxide solution was added and shaken vigorously where by a clear solution was obtained. This was kept overnight and then enough water was added to this clear solution for complete precipitation. A white precipitate was obtained. It was filtered; washed with enough cold water to make it free from alkali and then dried. The crude product was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. Homogeneity of the product was determined by tlc : (1) (68.8%), m.p. 135°C (Found : C, 79.58; H, 5.78; N, 7.15. C₁₃H₁₁NO requires : C, 79.17; H, 5.62; N, 7.10%); λ_{max} (log ε) 334.0 (3.15), 329.0 (3.05), 321.0 (3.20), 290.5 (3.93), 253.5 (3.78), 233.0 (4.37), 215.5 (4.15) nm; ν_{max} 3401.8 (OH), 3050.3–2915.9 (aromatic C-H), 1600.0 (aromatic residue), 1224.7 (C-N), 1137.3 cm⁻¹ (C-O stretching in alcohol); ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 2.7 (CH₂OH), 5.7 (2H, s, CH₂OH), 7.3–8.1 (8H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃) 120.4 (C-1), 123.7 (C-2), 120.2 (C-3), 108.8 (C-4), 109.6

(C-4a), 109.6 (C-4b), 108.8 (C-5), 120.2 (C-6), 123.7 (C-7), 120.4 (C-8), 139.8 (C-8a), 139.8 (C-9a), 66.7 (-CH₂OH); *m/z* 197, 167, 140.

N-Acetoxymethylenecarbazole (2) : 0.005 mol of *N*-hydroxymethylenecarbazole (1) was dissolved in minimum volume of acetic acid and to this solution, 25 ml of acetic anhydride was added and mixed properly. After that, the reaction mixture was heated strongly with simultaneous shaking till complete evaporation of the excess acetic anhydride, where by a white crystalline solid mass was obtained. This solid mass was separated and washed with water to make it acid free. It was then dried and then recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. Homogeneity of the product was determined by tlc : (2) (7.26%), m.p. 293°C (Found : C, 75.59; H, 5.50; N, 5.89. C₁₅H₁₃NO₂ requires : C, 75.30; H, 5.47; N, 5.85%); ν_{max} 3030 (aromatic C-H), 1600.0 (aromatic part), 1233.2 cm⁻¹ (acetate of saturated alcohol).

N-Bromomethylenecarbazole (3) : 0.005 mol of *N*-hydroxymethylenecarbazole (1) was completely dissolved in minimum volume of acetic acid. To this solution 48% hydrobromic acid was added drop wisely where by a curdy white precipitate was obtained. Addition of 48% hydrobromic acid was continued till the precipitation completed. It was then warmed and after that, the reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold water, where by a white solid was separated out. It was then filtered, washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and then by pure water. It was dried and then the crude product was recrystallised from methylenechloride. Homogeneity of the product was determined by tlc : (3) (4.36%), m.p. 235°C (Found : C, 61.81; H, 4.01; N, 5.39. C₁₃H₁₀NBr requires : C, 62.02; H, 3.87; N, 5.38%); ν_{max} 3030 (aromatic C-H), 1600.0 (aromatic residue), 1330, 1149 (-CH₂Br), 690, 515 cm⁻¹ (brominated compound).

N-Methoxymethylenecarbazole (4) : 0.005 mol of *N*-hydroxymethylenecarbazole (1) was dissolved in 25 ml of acetone and to this solution, 20 ml of 50% caustic potash solution was added, followed by shaking for 10–15 min. 10 ml of dimethyl sulphate was added to this solution and the reaction mixture was shaken for another 20 min. Then it was kept overnight. After that, the reaction mixture was poured into ice cold water; where by a white crystalline solid was separated out. It was filtered, washed with ice cold water, dried and then the crude product was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. Homogeneity of the product was determined by tlc : (4) (20.26%), m.p. 197°C (Found : C, 78.60; H, 6.11; N, 6.57. C₁₄H₁₃NO requires : C, 79.59; H, 6.20; N, 6.63%); ν_{max} 3030 (aromatic C-H), 1600 (aromatic residue), 1150–1085 cm⁻¹ (aliphatic ether linkage).

3,6,9-Trimethyl-1-isopentenylcarbazole (5) : 0.0004

mol of 3,6-dimethyl-1-isopentenylcarbazole was dissolved in 15 ml of dry acetone and this solution was shaken with 15 ml of dimethylsulphate and caustic potash (0.5 g/ml) for 1 h at room temperature. On standing for 48 h at room temperature, it furnished a crystalline mass. This was recrystallised from ethanol, a white, whereby the product was obtained as homogeneous, crystalline, white solid : (5) (50.0%), m.p. 142°C (Found : C, 86.63; H, 8.41; N, 5.07. C₂₀H₂₃N requires : C, 86.59; H, 8.35; N, 5.05%); λ_{\max} (log ϵ) 363.1 (3.754), 346.2 (3.733), 330.2 (3.733), 291.1 (4.498), 239.2 (4.509), 214.6 (3.978) nm; ν_{\max} 2947 (N-C-H), 1635 (CH=CH), 1600 (aromatic residue), 866 cm⁻¹ (aromatic substitution); ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 1.56 (6H, d, *J* 14.01 Hz, H-13/14), 1.62 (1H, m, H-12), 2.24 (3H, s, H-15), 2.41 (3H, s, H-16), 5.74 (1H, d, *J* 9.80 Hz, H-10), 7.24 (1H, t, *J* 9.02 Hz, H-11), 7.33 (1H, s, H-2), 7.21 (1H, d, *J* 10.24 Hz, H-7), 8.00 (1H, d, *J* 7.80 Hz, H-8), 7.45 (1H, s, H-4), 7.78 (1H, s, H-5), 4.21 (1H, s, N-CH₃); ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃) 117.43 (C-1), 118.84 (C-2), 128.78 (C-3), 119.34 (C-4), 124.55 (C-4a), 106.33 (C-4b), 119.37 (C-5), 136.48 (C-6), 119.26 (C-7), 108.59 (C-8), 123.44 (C-8a), 151.12 (C-9a), 121.63 (C-10), 142.04 (C-11), 33.30 (C-12), 27.56 (C-13/14), 16.71 (C-15/16), 33.30 (N-CH₃); *m/z* 277.

N-Acetyl-1,2,3,4,4a,9a-hexahydrocarbazole (*cis*) (6) : 0.006 mol of 1,2,3,4,4a,9a-hexahydrocarbazole (*cis*) was dissolved in minimum volume of acetic acid and to this solution, 25 ml of acetic anhydride was added and mixed thoroughly. After that, the reaction mixture was heated

strongly with simultaneous shaking till complete evaporation of the excess acetic anhydride added, where by a white crystalline solid mass was obtained. This solid mass was separated and washed with water to make it acid free. It was then dried and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. Homogeneity of the product was determined by tlc : (6) (25.60%), m.p. 98°C (lit.³ 98°C) (Found : C, 78.98; H, 8.10; N, 6.59. C₁₄H₁₅NO requires : C, 78.10; H, 7.96; N, 6.51%).

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. (Mrs.) A. Chatterjee, Department of Pure Chemistry, Calcutta University, Kolkata, India for her keen interest and help in various aspects of spectral measurements. R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Madras, India is also thanked for recording the spectra of some compounds. The authorities of Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan is also thanked for their help.

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